

1 **Rip kinase expression during early development in humans.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here dynamic Rip kinase
9 expression during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Liu, Y., Fan, C., Zhang, Y., Yu, X., Wu, X., Zhang, X., Zhao, Q., Zhang, H., Xie, Q., Li, M. and Li,
12 X., 2017. RIP1 kinase activity-dependent roles in embryonic development of Fadd-deficient mice. *Cell*
13 *Death & Differentiation*, 24(8), pp.1459-1469.